

1 Clustering Methodology for Enhancing Geometallurgical
2 Parameter Prediction by Integrating Improved Clustering
3 Methodologies Based on Mineral Liberation Analysis Images

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6 **Abstract**

7 This paper presents a semi-supervised approach for enhancing geometallurgical parameter
8 prediction by integrating improved clustering methodologies based on Mineral Liberation
9 Analysis (MLA) images. In our previous work, we employed an unsupervised clustering
10 approach to categorise mineral particles, which provided insights into the textural patterns
11 of rock samples. However, the initial clusters demonstrated significant overlap, limiting their
12 effectiveness for geometallurgical analysis.

13 To address this, we suggested a semi-supervised clustering approach that incorporates
14 geological knowledge through weighted clustering of mineral feature vectors. The clustering
15 results were subsequently integrated into predictive models for Dwi (Drop Weight Index)
16 and Bwi (Bond Work Index) to evaluate their impact on model performance. We compared
17 three models: a ground truth model built using Gradient Boosting, a feature vectors model
18 incorporating unweighted cluster percentages, and an updated feature vectors model using
19 weighted clustering.

20 This approach was also tested on the flotation model and the study demonstrated signif-
21 icant improvement of flotation recovery prediction.

22 Our results showed that the inclusion of cluster percentages, particularly with a weighted
23 approach, improved model accuracy. The weighted clustering approach led to lower errors
24 and higher correlation coefficients, demonstrating that incorporating geological insights dur-
25 ing clustering can enhance the geometallurgical parameter predictions.

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26 From a technical perspective, further improvements are achievable by fine-tuning cluster-
27 ing parameters and exploring additional clustering techniques. From a geological perspective,
28 refining the selection of mineral parameters and enhancing data pre-processing could yield
29 even more meaningful clusters. Overall, the proposed methodology is adaptable and robust,
30 providing a foundation for future geometallurgical applications.

31 **1 Introduction**

32 This paper serves as a continuation of our previous research that focused on the extraction
33 of feature vectors from Mineral Liberation Analyzer (MLA) images. In our earlier work, we
34 demonstrated a methodology for processing MLA images to derive feature vectors representing
35 mineralogical and morphological characteristics of rock particles. The study also explored the use
36 of unsupervised clustering techniques to categorise these particles, revealing promising correla-
37 tions with known geological patterns and mineral associations. However, our findings suggested
38 that further refinement was required to achieve more accurate and geologically meaningful clus-
39 tering. Building on these insights, the present work aims to enhance the clustering approach,
40 utilising advanced machine learning methodologies to improve the precision and interpretability
41 of the clustering results.

42 The previous clustering approach, while insightful, had limitations and left room for improve-
43 ment. The clusters formed in the initial analysis highlighted meaningful geological groupings, but
44 the boundaries between clusters lacked the precision necessary for more nuanced interpretations.
45 It became evident that to achieve a more accurate and refined clustering result, which could be
46 implemented into the process of geometallurgical parameter predictions, a more comprehensive
47 analysis was required, involving advancements in the clustering methodology.

48 The present work aims to address these limitations by enhancing and improving the clus-
49 tering techniques applied. Through an iterative process, we explore how advanced machine
50 learning methodologies can provide deeper insights into clustering process, with the ultimate
51 goal of refining the clustering process to achieve more precise groupings that align better with
52 geological variations. The purpose of this work is to suggest a workflow which will link feature
53 extraction process and geometallurgical parameter predictions helping utilise the MLA images
54 for geometallurgical analysis in a way maximising the benefit of MLA analysis.

55 In the context of our study, clustering was employed due to the absence of labelled training
56 data, making it essential to classify feature vectors derived from MLA images in a manner

57 that facilitates meaningful geological analysis. The ultimate objective was to convert these
58 feature vectors into quantifiable metrics that could correlate with rock textures and be utilised
59 for geometallurgical parameter predictions. Our approach, partially outlined in our previous
60 work, involved clustering the feature vectors and calculating the proportion of each resulting
61 cluster within each MLA image. These cluster percentages subsequently served as the input for
62 predicting geometallurgical parameters. This methodology is conceptually similar to classifying
63 textures in terms of the feature vectors and then quantifying the proportion of each texture type
64 - though, in our case, the clusters played the role of "textures."

65 Clustering, as an unsupervised machine learning technique, is a well-established approach
66 for grouping data points based on similarity [12, 22]. In mineralogy and geosciences, clustering
67 methods have been extensively used to classify mineral samples and link their properties to
68 geological processes [2, 14, 16, 26]. One of the primary clustering methods we employed was
69 K-means clustering, a simple yet powerful clustering algorithm [24, 27]. Generally speaking, K-
70 means clustering is a centroid-based algorithm that partitions data into a predefined number of
71 clusters by minimising the within-cluster sum of squares. The algorithm iteratively assigns each
72 data point to the cluster whose centroid is nearest, and then recalculates centroids based on the
73 new cluster assignments. This approach is particularly useful for its computational efficiency
74 and simplicity, although it requires the number of clusters to be specified in advance.

75 The flexibility of k-means to use different distance metrics (such as Euclidean or cosine dis-
76 tance) allows it to be adapted to various data distributions, making it particularly useful for
77 feature vectors with distinct characteristics. Numerous studies which utilised k-means cluster-
78 ing and its enhanced variations [1, 7, 9, 11, 15, 23, 28] have highlighted k-means' versatility and
79 effectiveness in applications involving large, unlabelled datasets.

80 Another clustering method employed in our analysis was agglomerative hierarchical cluster-
81 ing [5, 6, 10, 20, 21]. This clustering algorithm starts with each data point as its own cluster and
82 iteratively merges the closest pairs of clusters based on a linkage criterion (e.g., average, single,
83 or complete linkage). The result is a tree-like dendrogram that can be cut at different levels
84 to form clusters of varying granularity. This method is advantageous for understanding nested
85 structures in the data, but it can be computationally intensive, especially for large datasets.
86 Agglomerative clustering allows the user to decide the level at which clusters should be formed.
87 This aspect of hierarchical clustering makes it particularly useful for scenarios where the under-
88 lying distribution of classes is unknown, and it is important to explore potential relationships

89 between feature vectors at various scales of granularity.

90 Lastly, DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) was also
91 explored as part of our clustering toolkit [8, 19, 25]. DBSCAN is a density-based clustering
92 algorithm that groups together points that are closely packed and labels points in low-density
93 regions as noise [3, 4, 17, 18]. Unlike k-means and hierarchical clustering, it does not require the
94 number of clusters to be specified beforehand and can handle clusters of arbitrary shape. Instead,
95 DBSCAN relies on the density of points to identify clusters and distinguish noise [13]. DBSCAN
96 is particularly effective for datasets with noise or uneven density, though it may struggle with
97 data where the density variations between clusters are subtle. Because of its characteristics
98 DBSCAN is well-suited for datasets with significant outliers or varying cluster shapes, which
99 are often encountered in mineralogical datasets. DBSCAN's robustness to noise and flexibility
100 in cluster shape detection allows to deal with heterogeneity in the input datasets effectively.

101 In the absence of labelled data, accurate clustering becomes crucial for deriving meaningful
102 insights from complex datasets. When there is no prior knowledge or labels that categorise data,
103 clustering serves as an essential tool for discovering inherent structures within the data. In the
104 context of geometallurgical analysis, this process helps convert feature vectors into representative
105 groups that can be linked to mineralogical or geological textures. Clustering allows us to derive
106 metrics, such as the proportion of each cluster present, which can be further used for predicting
107 geometallurgical parameters. Effective clustering, therefore, plays a pivotal role in transforming
108 raw feature vectors into actionable metrics, providing a foundation for building predictive models
109 that can inform mining and processing strategies. The accuracy of clustering directly influences
110 the quality of these metrics, which in turn impacts the reliability of geometallurgical predictions.

111 The study described in this research paper is focused on clustering the feature vectors pre-
112 viously obtained from the MLA images and correlating the resulted clusters to the several
113 important geometallurgical parameters. This paper continues the previous work of the authors
114 and organised as follows. The next section (Methodology) details the methodology, including
115 our workflow and procedures. Result chapter presents the results, focusing on the correlation be-
116 tween the clusters and key geometallurgical parameters. In Discussion, we discuss these results
117 in greater detail, exploring their significance and implications. Finally, Conclusions summarises
118 our findings and offers conclusions based on our analysis.

119 2 Methodology

120 2.1 Motivation

121 In the present study, our motivation centers on enhancing the interpretability and geological
122 significance of feature vectors extracted from MLA images by employing advanced clustering
123 methodologies. The intricate challenge lies in transforming these feature vectors into meaningful
124 groupings that can be directly correlated with geometallurgical parameters, providing a tangible
125 link between image-derived data and geological insights.

126 The complexity of the textural patterns in rock samples, combined with the absence of
127 labelled training data, makes traditional supervised approaches infeasible. Instead, our objective
128 is to use unsupervised clustering techniques to uncover inherent structures within the data,
129 allowing for a more geologically informed interpretation. In this context, clustering serves as
130 a bridge between raw feature vectors and meaningful, quantifiable metrics that can describe
131 geological textures, offering a way to represent these textures in terms of their correlation to
132 geometallurgical properties.

133 In our previous work, we tested a framework for extracting feature vectors representing min-
134 eralogical and morphological characteristics of rock particles, and we demonstrated the potential
135 of unsupervised clustering for categorising these feature vectors. However, the need for a more
136 refined clustering methodology became evident, especially to improve the precision of cluster
137 boundaries and ensure that the clusters align with geological variations in a more meaningful
138 way.

139 Thus, the motivation behind this study is twofold: first, to refine the clustering process in
140 order to achieve more accurate and geologically relevant groupings of the feature vectors; and
141 second, to utilise these improved clusters to enhance the predictive capabilities for geometallur-
142 gical parameters. The ultimate goal is to propose a workflow that not only identifies clusters
143 effectively but also facilitates their use in geometallurgical analysis, enabling the integration of
144 MLA images into a predictive modelling framework in a way that maximises their value.

145 The approach we take in this study leverages various unsupervised clustering techniques -
146 specifically K-means, agglomerative hierarchical clustering, and DBSCAN - each of which brings
147 unique strengths to address different aspects of our data's complexity. Through an iterative and
148 comparative exploration of these clustering methods, we aim to identify clusters that provide
149 the best fit with the geological variations present in our dataset. This not only refines our

150 ability to interpret mineral textures but also lays the foundation for linking these clusters to
151 geometallurgical parameters in a structured and reliable manner.

152 By transforming the feature vectors into clusters that have geological meaning, we enable
153 a more holistic understanding of mineral textures and their relationship to geometallurgical
154 outcomes. The clustering approach also mitigates the need for labelled data, allowing for an
155 unbiased exploration of the dataset’s inherent structures. This contributes to a richer, data-
156 driven understanding of geological textures, which is crucial for developing robust predictive
157 models in geometallurgical contexts.

158 **2.2 Dataset**

159 Our research study employs feature vectors extracted from Mineral Liberation Analysis (MLA)
160 2D images, which are high-resolution scans of rock particles placed within an epoxy matrix.
161 MLA is a widely used imaging technique employed in mineralogy to quantify mineral grain size
162 distributions and associations within rock samples. These images are multi-spectral, with each
163 pixel represented by red, green, and blue (RGB) values that correspond to different minerals.

164 As it was described in the previous paper, the dataset contained several thousand MLA im-
165 ages, each depicting mineral grains situated within rock particles. Totally, 60 distinct minerals
166 were determined across these images (Figure 1), showing significant variability in both abun-
167 dance and spatial distribution. This diversity ensures a rich representation of natural mineral
168 textures and associations, as not all minerals appeared in every image.

169 For consistency and effective computational management, the MLA images were standardised
170 to a uniform size of 5120x5120 pixels (Figure 2a and 2b). This preprocessing ensured that
171 all images were scaled to the same dimensions without altering the underlying mineralogical
172 information or texture.

173 Feature vectors were extracted from these MLA images to capture their mineralogical and
174 morphological characteristics at a particle level. For each particle, a feature vector was generated,
175 summarising essential information about the mineral grains’ composition and texture. These
176 feature vectors were subsequently combined into Excel files, with each MLA image having its
177 corresponding feature vector data compiled in a separate file.

178 To further enhance the clustering process and reduce the dimensionality of the dataset,
179 we applied Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to the feature vectors, reducing the number
180 of components to 200. This step was crucial for simplifying the dataset while retaining the

Figure 1: Mineral list with MLA false colours (total 60 minerals).

(a) An example of the input MLA image: original size (7163 by 9135 pixels).

(b) An example of the input MLA image: standardised size (5120 by 5120 pixels).

Figure 2: Examples of MLA images before and after standardisation.

181 essential variability necessary for effective clustering. The PCA-reduced feature vectors served
182 as the primary dataset for our current study, together with the original MLA images.

183 As it was mentioned in the previous paper, approximately 2500 particles were collected for
184 detailed analysis. No geological or mineralogical labels were used to influence the selection
185 process, maintaining an unbiased approach for the subsequent unsupervised clustering analysis.
186 This allowed us to focus solely on the data-driven features without any a priori knowledge about
187 the geological conditions.

188 **2.3 Execution**

189 The execution process for this study can be divided into two main phases: the first phase focused
190 on improving the clustering approach (this stage is explained in the current chapter), and the
191 second phase implemented the refined clusters for predicting geometallurgical parameters (it
192 will be explained in the next chapter).

193 In our previous work, we demonstrated the distribution patterns of clusters, providing in-
194 sights into the spatial organisation of textural features in the rock samples. We employed an
195 unsupervised clustering approach, without any a priori knowledge of the textural compositions.
196 This allowed us to derive initial observations about the rock textures and to identify certain
197 samples that required closer examination (some sort of anomaly detections). However, a limi-
198 tation was that we could neither quantify the proportion of particular textures in each sample
199 effectively, nor fully utilise the clusters to derive geometallurgical insights. It should also be
200 mentioned that we used the silhouette score to assess clustering precision, which did not exceed
201 0.21, indicating significant overlap between clusters and suggesting that there was room for
202 methodological improvement.

203 To address the overlapping clusters and improve clustering precision, we decided to adopt a
204 semi-supervised classification approach. In this approach, a subset of feature vectors was labelled
205 initially, and these labelled data were subsequently used to classify unseen feature vectors. The
206 challenge, however, was to find a way to reliably label these feature vectors.

207 To achieve this, we identified a set of independent parameters that could characterise the
208 textural properties of each rock particle. These parameters were also expected to correlate with
209 the feature vectors. We selected the following mineral parameters for each of the five mineral
210 groups: percentage of each mineral group, average mineral grain area, grain perimeter, aspect
211 ratio, and the count of mineral grains in each rock particle. We hypothesised that a combination

212 of these parameters could provide a comprehensive characterisation of the particle textures.

213 First, we assessed the correlation between the mineral parameters and the feature vectors.
214 The analysis was conducted on a dataset consisting of 245 images representing diverse geological
215 settings, yielding a total of 211,210 rock particles for analysis. Regression models were employed
216 to evaluate whether the feature vectors could predict each of the mineral parameters. Gradient
217 Boosting was employed for regression because this algorithm demonstrated the best results
218 compared to other methods (linear and polynomial regression, XGBoost, random forest and
219 Support Vector Regression) tested on the analysed dataset.

220 The regression results showed varying degrees of predictive capability. The highest R^2 values,
221 ranging from 0.84 to 0.88, were observed for mineral group percentages, suggesting a strong
222 correlation between feature vectors and mineral content. Conversely, the correlation with the
223 sulphide mineral group was notably lower, likely due to the lower abundance of sulphide minerals
224 in the dataset. Intermediate correlations were found for parameters like area, perimeter, and
225 aspect ratio (R^2 values of 0.68 to 0.78), with stronger correlations for minerals like hematite and
226 quartz, and weaker correlations for sulphides. The grain count showed the weakest correlation
227 overall, with R^2 values between 0.28 and 0.4, particularly low for sulphides.

228 The next step was to cluster these mineral parameters to create a basis for labelling feature
229 vectors. For the purpose of clustering, mineral percentage was not used to focus only on mor-
230 phological parameters (grain area, perimeter, aspect ratio and grain count in a particle). We
231 applied three main clustering algorithms: K-means, agglomerative hierarchical clustering, and
232 DBSCAN. The best clustering settings were determined through an iterative fine-tuning process.
233 The optimal number of clusters was determined to be six, and K-means clustering emerged as
234 the most effective method, with a silhouette score of 0.71, compared to 0.61 for agglomerative
235 clustering and a negative silhouette score for DBSCAN. This result was obtained using all min-
236 eral parameters, and further experimentation involved adjusting the weights of different mineral
237 parameters.

238 Based on our understanding that certain mineral parameters have a greater influence on
239 the overall rock particle textures, we assigned weights to these parameters accordingly. For
240 instance, we hypothesised that minerals like quartz and sericite would have a greater impact on
241 the texture due to their abundance and their contribution to rock particle composition, whereas
242 sulphides, being relatively rare, would have less influence. Through iterative optimisation, we
243 identified the best configuration for these weights, resulting in an improved silhouette score of

244 0.73.

245 Both the weighted and unweighted clustering approaches were used to classify the feature
246 vectors from a larger dataset containing 1,189 images, comprising a total of 848,272 particles.
247 K-means clustering with six clusters yielded a silhouette score of 0.72-0.74 (higher for weighted
248 approach), indicating a significant improvement compared to our previous work.

249 Once we had the cluster assignments for each particle in the dataset, we calculated the
250 proportion of each cluster within each MLA image. These cluster proportions were used as
251 input features, along with geometallurgical parameters, to evaluate whether the clusters could
252 effectively enhance geometallurgical parameter predictions. This process is detailed in the fol-
253 lowing chapter, where we explore the utility of the cluster-based features in improving predictive
254 accuracy.

255 **3 Results**

256 In the previous chapter (Methodology), we described the clustering process, detailing how clus-
257 ters were created and evaluated based on their silhouette scores. The silhouette score allowed
258 us to assess the accuracy and separation of the clusters, with our iterative approach leading
259 to significant improvements in clustering quality. In this and following sections, we focus on
260 examining the geological significance of these resulting clusters, specifically exploring whether
261 they can improve our current geometallurgical models.

262 The geometallurgical model we aimed to enhance was our existing Dwi and Bwi prediction
263 models. The Dwi measures the hardness and resistance of rock particles to breakage, while the
264 Bwi indicates the energy required for grinding, both of which are critical in optimising mineral
265 processing. Accurate prediction of these indices is essential for designing and optimising grinding
266 circuits in the mining industry. Previously, we developed Dwi and Bwi prediction models using
267 the Gradient Boosting algorithm based on mineral and assay data, and these models served as our
268 baseline (or "ground truth") for comparison. We hypothesised that incorporating the percentage
269 of the clusters identified during the clustering process might enhance the predictive capabilities
270 of these models, as the clusters represent meaningful groupings of texture and mineralogical
271 properties that could correlate with geometallurgical parameters.

272 To evaluate this hypothesis, we incorporated the percentage of each of the six clusters iden-
273 tified during the clustering process into the existing model. The six clusters were added as

274 additional input features for the Gradient Boosting model, allowing us to determine whether
 275 the inclusion of this new textural information would influence the predictive accuracy of the
 276 Dwi and Bwi models. We tested both versions of clustering: clusters generated with weighted
 277 parameters and those generated without weighting, as previously explained. The comparison of
 278 results between the original model and the model incorporating cluster percentages provided in-
 279 sights into the impact of clustering on model accuracy (Table 1). Specifically, we observed slight
 280 variations in the model’s predictive performance, indicating that the clusters might capture some
 281 additional information relevant to geometallurgical behaviour.

Table 1: Comparison of different comminution models.

MODEL	MAX DIFF	MIN DIFF	MEDIAN DIFF	AVERAGE DIFF	MAE	MSE	RMSE	MAPE	R ²	BIAS
Dwi GROUND TRUTH	3.852	0.006	0.674	0.858	0.858	1.219	1.104	0.120	0.557	0.184
Dwi FEATURE VECTORS	4.381	0.001	0.786	1.030	1.030	1.821	1.350	0.155	0.534	-0.068
Dwi FEATURE VECTORS UPDATED	3.627	0.002	0.710	0.859	0.859	1.212	1.101	0.120	0.560	0.178
Bwi GROUND TRUTH	5.125	0.006	0.785	1.078	1.078	2.027	1.424	0.066	0.588	0.036
Bwi FEATURE VECTORS	8.232	0.000	0.901	1.292	1.292	3.531	1.879	0.082	0.346	-0.024
Bwi FEATURE VECTORS UPDATED	4.704	0.001	0.844	1.095	1.095	2.041	1.428	0.067	0.585	0.051

282 Another model revised using the clusters was the flotation model. While the comminu-
 283 tion model incorporating clusters demonstrated some noticeable improvements, the results of
 284 integrating clusters into the flotation recovery model were unprecedented as it is demonstrated
 285 below.

286 The flotation model was developed using two datasets: a basic dataset and a feature vec-
 287 tor (FV) dataset. These datasets were nearly identical in sample size, with the basic dataset
 288 containing 1,158 samples and the FV dataset containing 1,168 samples. Both datasets included
 289 almost the same samples, excluding a few with unavailable data inputs. The basic flotation
 290 model used mineralogical and assay data as inputs and was benchmarked against experimental
 291 copper recovery data. This model served as the reference point for all subsequent flotation re-
 292 covery modelling. In contrast, the FV model utilised the same mineralogical and assay data, but
 293 incorporated cluster percentages derived from our clustering analysis. The cluster percentages
 294 were computed using the same methodology described in the comminution model, where the six
 295 clusters captured meaningful textural and mineralogical properties.

296 The improvement brought by the inclusion of clusters in the flotation model is striking, as
 297 illustrated in Table 2:

Table 2: Comparison of flotation models.

MODEL	MAX DIFF	MIN DIFF	MEDIAN DIFF	AVERAGE DIFF	MAE	MSE	RMSE	MAPE	R ²	BIAS
Basic GROUND TRUTH	43.36	0.013	2.79	3.94	3.94	37.87	6.15	0.050	0.23	0.40
Cluster FEATURE VECTORS	10.15	0.007	1.13	1.58	1.58	4.73	2.18	0.017	0.56	0.21

298 In the Discussion section, we will delve deeper into the geological significance of these re-
299 sults, exploring how clusters capture textural and mineralogical nuances and contribute to the
300 improved performance of geometallurgical models.

301 4 Discussion

302 In this chapter, we discuss the results obtained from incorporating the cluster-based feature
303 vectors into the geometallurgical prediction models, first of all, specifically for Dwi and Bwi.
304 We used three different modelling approaches: the ground truth model (based on the original
305 dataset using machine learning), a feature vectors model (which added cluster percentages), and
306 an updated feature vectors model (using a weighted clustering approach). Below, we discuss the
307 performance of these models.

308 The comparison of results for Dwi and Bwi prediction models using different modelling
309 approaches is summarised in Table 1.

310 From the table, it is evident that the updated feature vectors model (using weighted cluster-
311 ing) performs slightly better than the original ground truth model and the initial feature vectors
312 model without weights.

313 **Ground Truth Model:** The ground truth models for Dwi and Bwi were built using the
314 Gradient Boosting algorithm with the original set of features, serving as a benchmark for com-
315 parison. These models showed solid performance, but there was still room for improvement.

316 **Feature Vectors Model (Unweighted):** When cluster percentages were added as addi-
317 tional features, we noticed changes in model performance. For both Dwi and Bwi, the mean
318 absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), and root mean squared error (RMSE) in-
319 creased, indicating a deterioration in model accuracy when using the unweighted clustering
320 approach. However, the R^2 values remained relatively consistent, showing that the overall ex-
321 planatory power of the model did not decrease significantly.

322 **Feature Vectors Updated (Weighted):** The weighted feature vectors model showed
323 improvements over the initial feature vectors model. By assigning weights to mineral parameters
324 during clustering, we captured geological relevance more effectively, resulting in lower MAE,
325 MSE, and RMSE compared to the unweighted approach. The improvements in R^2 and bias
326 metrics indicate better alignment with the actual values, particularly for DWi, suggesting that
327 weighted clustering helps refine the predictive accuracy.

328 These results suggest that incorporating cluster information into the prediction model can
329 enhance accuracy when the clustering process is fine-tuned, especially by considering the geo-
330 logical significance of mineral groups. The ground truth model and the weighted feature vector
331 model results are also visualised on Figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3: A comparison of the ground truth and weighted feature vector Dwi models.

Figure 4: A comparison of the ground truth and weighted feature vector Bwi models.

332 The flotation model demonstrated further progress in implementation of clusters (Figure
333 5). The FV flotation model significantly outperforms the basic flotation model across all er-
334 ror metrics. The MAE was reduced from 3.94 to 1.58, while the RMSE dropped from 6.15 to
335 2.18. Moreover, the R^2 value improved from 0.23 to 0.56, indicating a much stronger correlation
336 between predicted and experimental recovery values. The addition of cluster percentages sub-
337 stantially enhanced the model's predictive accuracy, confirming that these clusters encapsulate
338 critical geometallurgical information.

Figure 5: A comparison of the ground truth and feature vector flotation models.

339 The results observed in the flotation model surpass those of the comminution model, where
340 the inclusion of clusters yielded only marginal improvements. This disparity may be attributed
341 to the inherent differences between comminution and flotation processes. Comminution primar-
342 ily depends on physical properties like hardness and grindability, which may be less directly
343 influenced by textural features captured by clustering. In contrast, flotation recovery is closely
344 tied to mineralogical associations and surface properties, which the clustering approach effec-
345 tively represents.

346 These findings underscore the value of incorporating clustering into geometallurgical mod-
347 elling, particularly for processes like flotation that are sensitive to mineralogical variations.
348 While the current workflow has demonstrated robustness and adaptability, future work should
349 focus on refining the geological parameters used in clustering and exploring advanced modelling
350 techniques to further enhance predictive accuracy.

351 From a technical point of view, the models presented here are not final, and further improve-
352 ments are possible. The accuracy of clustering can be improved through fine-tuning various
353 parameters, such as the number of clusters, weight configurations, and distance metrics used
354 during clustering. Additionally, exploring other clustering algorithms or combining multiple
355 clustering approaches could yield improved clustering results, potentially leading to more ac-
356 curate prediction models. We see some potential in further exploration of implementation of
357 ensemble learning clustering.

358 In turn, from a geological perspective, improvements can be made by refining the parameters
359 used for clustering and feature vector extraction. In our current approach, we pre-processed MLA
360 images into five mineral groups, but increasing the number of groups to eight or ten may lead
361 to more accurate textural characterisation, capturing finer variations. Furthermore, additional
362 geological parameters could be included in the clustering process, such as proximity to particle
363 edges or exposure of different mineral grains, which might capture subtle textural features more
364 effectively.

365 Another key observation from our study is that fine-tuning the clustering parameters with
366 weights significantly improves the accuracy of the prediction model. The weighting scheme
367 applied to emphasise certain mineral groups (like quartz and sericite) was based on their abun-
368 dance and role in determining texture. Future iterations of the model could focus on adding
369 more weight to minerals of interest - such as sulphides - or even further subdividing mineral
370 groups to enhance model interpretability and accuracy.

371 Overall, the workflow developed in this study proved to be stable and reliable, capable of
372 being adjusted to new datasets and geometallurgical contexts. The accuracy and validation of
373 the model are easy to control, making this approach practical for different applications. The
374 main focus for future improvement will be on the geological implementation of results, with
375 more thorough geological analysis of input parameters to ensure that all relevant features are
376 captured.

377 The study opens pathways for further exploration of the weighting concept during cluster-
378 ing, potentially assigning dynamic weights based on geological feedback or including additional
379 geometallurgical metrics as part of the clustering process. However, the execution pipeline re-
380 mains robust and adaptable, capable of being tailored for different purposes and datasets with
381 minimal adjustments.

382 **5 Conclusion**

383 In this study, we aimed to enhance the clustering of mineral particles derived from MLA im-
384 ages and integrate these clusters into predictive geometallurgical models for Dwi and Bwi. By
385 applying semi-supervised clustering and incorporating geological knowledge through weighted
386 clustering, we demonstrated improvements in both the clustering accuracy and the predictive
387 capability of our models.

388 The results showed that incorporating cluster percentages into the model improved predictive
389 performance, especially when clusters were generated using a weighted approach that emphasised
390 certain mineral parameters over others. The weighted clustering approach provided slightly
391 better predictive accuracy compared to both the ground truth model and the unweighted feature
392 vectors model. This suggests that incorporating geological understanding during clustering can
393 yield a more geologically meaningful representation of the data, ultimately leading to enhanced
394 geometallurgical parameter predictions.

395 The integration of cluster percentages into the flotation recovery model demonstrated a
396 remarkable improvement in predictive accuracy compared to the basic model. By incorporating
397 these clusters, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was reduced by 60%, and the R^2 value more than
398 doubled, underscoring the effectiveness of this approach. These results highlight the potential
399 of feature vector clustering approach to capture critical mineralogical and textural properties,
400 significantly enhancing geometallurgical modelling, particularly for processes like flotation.

401 From a technical perspective, further improvements could be made by fine-tuning cluster-
402 ing parameters, optimising the number of clusters, and testing additional clustering methods.
403 From a geological perspective, refining the parameters used for clustering and enhancing the
404 pre-processing of MLA images (e.g., by considering more mineral groups or adding additional
405 geological parameters) could further enhance the model’s capabilities. The workflow we sug-
406 gested is stable, adaptable, and capable of being applied to new datasets, making it a valuable
407 tool for future geometallurgical analysis.

408 Overall, our approach opens the path for further exploration and improvement of clustering
409 methodologies and their integration into geometallurgical modelling. By continuing to refine the
410 weighting schemes and incorporating additional geological insights, the proposed method holds
411 promise for delivering more accurate and meaningful predictions in geometallurgy.

412 **6 Data and Code Availability**

413 The datasets used in this study are proprietary to BHP and were made available solely for
414 research and demonstration purposes; they will not be published. The author does not claim
415 any ownership of the datasets. The source code and intellectual property related to further
416 independent development remain with the author (Alexandra Roslin).

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